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Tourism Enterprise Climate Action Literacy: Emissions Measurement, Monitoring & Reporting

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Further Reading:

Conefrey, A. & Hanrahan, J.
(2025) Tourism Enterprise's Level
of Climate Action Literacy and
Measuring, Monitoring and
Reporting of Emissions, *Tourism:
An International Interdisciplinary
Journal*, 7(2), 367-380
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Rationale, Aims and Objectives

This study evaluates climate action literacy among tourism enterprises and their efforts to measure, monitor, and report emissions. Integrating climate action into tourism policies is vital for sustainable development and aligns with the EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (2022), requiring environmental and social reporting by 2028. Using UN, UNWTO, and SDG frameworks, the study identifies gaps between theory and practice. Achieving Net-Zero demands a skilled, climate-literate workforce capable of implementing decarbonisation strategies. Policymakers should prioritise training, standardised reporting, and workforce development to strengthen tourism's climate contribution. Building enterprise capacity will ensure transparency, compliance, and long-term progress toward sustainable, low-carbon tourism.

Research Findings

Findings show major gaps in tourism enterprises' climate action and Net-Zero readiness. While most know 2030 goals, awareness of 2050 decarbonisation targets is limited. Terms like "decarbonisation" and "Net-Zero destination" are poorly understood, leading to weak implementation. Only 14% measure emissions, mostly via consultants, with little focus on indirect (Scope 2–3) emissions. This lack of capacity and transparency hinders progress and risks EU compliance. Policymakers must promote clear terminology, training, and reskilling to improve measurement and reporting. Strengthening literacy, embedding decarbonisation, and fostering collaboration are vital to align tourism with Net-Zero and the UN SDGs.

Policy Implications

Sustainable tourism depends on monitoring of environmental performance, with enterprises playing a key role by measuring and reporting emissions to track decarbonisation progress. However, while this study's small sample size limits representativeness and its focus on one destination reduces global applicability, it does offer early insights into climate action literacy that can guide wider sectoral learning. The lack of longitudinal tracking restricts understanding of progress in climate literacy and decarbonisation. External factors such as market, economic, and regulatory conditions were not considered, though they affect climate action adoption. Policymakers should prioritise standardised reporting frameworks, targeted training and consistent guidance, while systemic changes are needed to support capacity building, enable transparent data collection and encourage sustained climate action across the sector.

Industry Recommendations

To enable tourism's transition to Net-Zero by 2050, urgent action is required to reskill and upskill the workforce for a decarbonised future. While enterprises demonstrate climate action literacy and acknowledge their role in emission reduction, significant gaps remain in implementation and long-term preparedness. Under EU law, all enterprises must report sustainability impacts by 2028, making workforce training in emission measurement, monitoring, and reporting essential. Policymakers should promote standardised frameworks, international collaboration, and longitudinal research to assess progress and address regional challenges. Future policies must integrate economic, regulatory, and environmental factors to encourage industry-wide participation and transparency. Strengthening capacity, aligning with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, and fostering evidence-based practices will ensure tourism contributes effectively to global climate action and sustainable development goals.

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